

Short Circuit and Avalanche Effects in 12V Power Distribution for Automated Driving

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Abstract—For the legal deployment of automated vehicles the power distribution within is a key topic. This system has to be fail-operational in case of faults to reach the safe state according to the standard. Switching off loads and short circuits is driving the required switches into avalanche. Exceeding the avalanche energy destroys the device and the system might change into an unsafe state. Through creating a fail-operational power distribution, electric parameters are changing and not all effects are visible immediately. This paper shows results of the SPICE simulation under worst case conditions to analyze specific electric influences within a fail-operational power distribution. Furthermore, not all devices which are expected to go into avalanche are driven into avalanche.

Index Terms—fail-operational power distribution, avalanche effect, SPICE simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of automated driving has begun and is progressing rapidly. Traditional OEMs and new players are working hard to bring highly and fully automated vehicles onto the market. Sensors, fusion units and controllers are defining the possibilities of detecting obstacles and avoiding crashes in first case. These need to be powered up through the power distribution in the vehicle. Concepts of how specific functions can be fail-operational are shown in [1]. How the energy is supplied to the functions itself has not been discussed. A critical fault in the power distribution may lead to a loss of control of the function and in worst case of the vehicle. Concepts for a fail-operational power distribution has been shown in [2] and how they might work in [3]. Semiconductor switches inside of these distribution concepts avoid inadmissible currents or voltages by switching loads (or faulty branches) in case of a fault. They may experience extreme stress.

In this work we analyze the avalanche effect, which occurs always if a MOSFET is switched off and the residual current is not freewheeled. Avalanche itself happens for any MOSFET during the time between conduction to disconnection. The space charge inside of the pn junction loses its insulating property if higher voltage occurs. The high voltage accelerates the charge carriers such that new carriers are generated through impact ionization [4]. Critical is the energy the device has to dissipate during avalanche. Exceeding this limit destroys the device. While in power converters the currents are well defined, the current consumption in vehicles is depending on

many factors. A test sequence has been shown in [5] with the current consumption for maneuvers. For a single and state of the art power distribution, the currents can easily be defined through the power consumption. Within a fail-operational power net for automated driving at least two independent sources are present and event more loads are attached to the system, hence the calculation is getting more complex.

II. CONCEPT BACKGROUND

Proposals for fail-operational power distribution have already been made in 2015 [6] or later in [7]. Even further in [6] the basic idea of a bidirectional MOSFET is being shown. The time in which a semiconductor switch can act is much faster than the times considered for a voltage drop. In [2], a closer look on the interconnection has been made and possible architectural concepts have been proposed. The favored proposal is shown in Fig. 1 including the different semiconductor switches required for the fail-operational power distribution. These are the "Safety Load Shut-off Switch" (SLS) - green, the "Battery Switch" (SBS) - yellow - and the "Back-to-Back Switch" (B2B) - blue. All of them serve a different purpose but are required to achieve the higher goal of the fail-operational and fault tolerant power distribution.

For the conception of a fail-operational power distribution, it does not matter if it is a 48V-hybrid vehicle or a high voltage vehicle. The power will be transferred in any case through the DCDC to supply the 12V power net and charge the batteries. For the high voltage system, an isolated DCDC is used to ensure electrical safety.

A. Battery Switch

The SBS can be a replacement for the pyroelectric fuse on one side, major target is the high current relays. It might carry the currents for turning on the electric starter of an internal combustion engine. In normal operation, it should be connected to charge the battery. If the generation is not present, it should deliver energy from the battery to the relevant loads. In fault condition, it should be turned off to protect the battery, if necessary. Energy transfer from the battery to the loads is prevented. Since the SBS is unidirectional, the battery could still be charged. The SBS should be located closely to the battery (Fig. 2) while all the loads will be

Fig. 1. L4/L5 dual DCDC supply concept

Fig. 2. SBS simplified circuit incl. freewheeling

supplied through the SBS. A freewheeling diode is useful to dissipate the current stored in the wire inductance to the load. If the battery features a battery management system (BMS) no current, voltage measurement is needed, because it is done within the BMS. Lithium-Ion batteries require a BMS. The SBS has to withstand cranking currents as maximum rating and as continuous the base load. In theory the tripping point could be changed to adapt to the needs of the vehicle.

B. Safety Load Shut-Off Switch

The SLS (Fig. 3) is a more complex switch. It should be able to measure currents and shut them off in case of overcurrent, creating a fuse like behavior. Melting fuses usually act slowly and do have a process deviation of the tripping point. An electronic fuse can mimic this blowing point. Even more, they can be set accurately to protect not only the supply but further the wire and the load attached. The precise setting of the tripping point could be done either by hardware or by a master unit which might overrule the intended tripping point shortly. In general, the wire harness could be optimized to decrease the weight if such switches are placed within. Lastly, an electronic fuse is not prone to be replaced with a wrong fuse by the end customer, if it is blown. The SLS can be used as a smart switch to throw off unnecessary loads in case of failure at any location or as smart fuse if a short circuit is within the harness after the switch.

C. Back-to-Back Switch

Depending on the overall architecture of the power distribution, it might carry starting currents or not. It is required in

Fig. 3. SLS simplified circuit

Fig. 4. B2B simplified circuit

all locations, where two energy supplies have to be connected. The B2B places MOSFETs in anti-series to be able to block the current in both directions. Due to the physical structure of single MOSFETs an integrated body diode is always present and conducts in reverse direction. A simple figure of the principal idea is shown in Fig. 4. During standard operation the B2B carries up to 250A, only during cranking or short circuit the current is higher.

III. SIMULATION SETUP

The shown concept has to work in most conditions without problems. One of the worst conditions is a low ohmic short circuit of the system. The rise of the current is limited by the wire inductance and the resistance with the time constant: $\tau_{SC} = \frac{L}{R}$. Still all batteries and DCDCs in the system could be supplying the short circuit, contributing to the short circuit current differently. Quite often, it is missed, that the energy supplies affect the avalanche energy. Thereby, during a switch off, the semiconductors are under harsh conditions. For the simulation, SPICE has been used for a more detailed view on the transistors.

To simplify the simulation and reduce the simulation time changes to the distribution have been made. The overall circuitry has been adapted to figure 5. Only the output capacitance of the DCDC has been used, which in first case is contributing to any short circuit. The inductors of the DCDC are delaying further power transfer until the control of the DCDC will shut it off, due to overload.

For the battery, the Rint model has been chosen [8] with an internal resistance of $3m\Omega$ for a single LiFePo4-cell [9]; resulting in $4m\Omega$ for a 12V battery pack with 60Ah. Such a battery is minimum required to operate an automated vehicle for 15min if the alternator or the DCDC is not working [2].

Fig. 5. Simulation circuit for short circuit

Fig. 6. Schematic of the hardware demonstrator for the driver input

	Value	Remarks
Battery Capacity	60Ah	-
Battery Internal DC Resistance	4mΩ	AMP20M1HD
MOSFET Model	IPLU300N04S4-R8	-
MOSFET Driver Model	AUIR3241STR	-
Fail-Op Load Resistor	200mΩ	50A
Load Resistor	150mΩ	90A
Short Circuit Resistor	1mΩ	limited by $\frac{di}{dt}$
Wire Inductance Battery Path	8μH	50mm ²
Wire Inductance Fail-Op Path	2μH and 1.5μH	-
Wire Inductance B2B Path	3μH	-
Wire Inductance Load Path	6μH	-
Short Circuit Inductance	100nH	-

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Consumer loads were not considered for the calculation of the battery size.

The loads have been assumed as single resistors adapted to the overall consumption for their specific use. For the fail-operational applications, an average 50A has been considered. The non-relevant loads with roughly 90A. Furthermore, the wire inductance have been brought into the concept, because they are driving the current forward and are critical. For the battery paths, a wire inductance of each 8μH was assumed, resembling a long cable with 50mm² thickness. Single battery driven systems have up to 15μH wire inductance, eventually even longer. Position of the battery, the possible short circuit, the position of the loads and the switches are defining the different inductance. Assumptions and estimations have had to be made.

The SPICE models of the IPLU300N04S4-R8 MOSFET and the AUIR3241STR driver have been used. The short circuit itself has been modelled with an 1mΩ resistor and a 100nH inductance and introduced in one path for the fail-operational applications, indicated by the red circle in figure 5. All the values are summarized in table I.

Furthermore, the simulation was set up with the elements of a real hardware demonstrator. The driver circuitry has been adapted such that the switch can work in 12V and 24V applications. The schematic of the driver input circuitry can be seen in figure 6. Based on this solution, an additional delay of about 15μs results.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation has been run until the steady state of the distribution network has been reached. Then a short-circuit has been introduced, starting after 12ms until the switch off command to the switching elements (B2B and SBS) were sent out with a small delay between them. The short circuit current reaches up to 1000A after 350μs. Thereby, exceeding the threshold values for standard operation of the switches. The SBS current rises to 400A, which flows through the B2B switch from the second battery combined with the current of the DCDC. The avalanche energy has been calculated with the power dissipated at the device and triangular integrated over the time until the current flowing through the device reached zero.

Comparing the same switches in the different configuration, it can be seen, that the ringing from figure 8 does slightly influence the B2B switch (figure 7) between after 12.41ms have passed in the simulation. Furthermore, the ringing is present on the second battery. Comparing to the freewheeling solution, the waveforms are much smoother. The avalanche duration for the SBS switch decreased to 1%, while the energy dissipated in the switch even further to 0.375%. The calculated values for comparison are shown in table II.

There are a couple of effects to be considered. Usually the energy supplies and inductances are contributing to the avalanche energy [10]. In a specific power distribution configuration, like the presented one, it might be assumed that all supplies must be considered. In this simulation, only the DCDC is contributing as energy supply to the B2B and even there, the energy is reduced. Because the other B2B is conducting, a freewheeling path is available for the energy fed from the DCDC. Loads can still be active.

We examine, that even though the B2B does experience a higher maximum power, the freewheeling path inside of the B2B reduces the overall avalanche energy. Furthermore, the maximum peak power during avalanche for the freewheeling path at the B2B is equivalent to the SBS freewheeling path. The duration of the conduction is different, resulting in a different dissipated energy.

Fig. 7. Simulation result for B2B at the Short Circuit Event without freewheeling at the SBS

Fig. 10. Simulation result for B2B at the Short Circuit Event with freewheeling at the SBS

Fig. 8. Simulation result for SBS at the Short Circuit Event - without freewheeling

Fig. 11. Simulation result for SBS at the Short Circuit Event - Freewheeling included

Fig. 9. Simulation result for the battery voltages - without freewheeling

Fig. 12. Simulation result for the battery voltages - with freewheeling

Fig. 13. Simulation result for the freewheeling path at the B2B

Fig. 14. Simulation result for the freewheeling path at the SBS

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

As pointed out in [10], avalanche is a critical operation point for MOSFETs and has to be considered carefully. Relays do see the same stress, and the arcs are occurring in such situations. The wire harness of vehicles is vast and complex. A detailed analysis of the whole system is getting more difficult. Considerations have to be made such that the design for the power distribution of automated driving can act quickly and is in the range of the Safe Operation Area of the semiconductors. As seen in the simulation, the energy to dissipate within the

	Energy	Power max.	Duration
B2B	442.99mJ	18.41kW	57.02μs
SBS	869.35mJ	18.39kW	94.70μs
B2B Freewheeling	72.92mJ	14.50kW	16.80μs
SBS Freewheeling	3.26mJ	6.24kW	0.93μs
FW Path B2B	174.90mJ	5.81kW	0.58ms
FW Path SBS	465.3mJ	5.81kW	3.17ms

TABLE II
SIMULATION RESULTS

MOSFET is high. Freewheeling diodes or MOSFETs can help mitigate the problem and reduce the avalanche stress of the switching element. Convergency issues did appear, if the SBS and the B2B were switched off exactly at the same time. This has been solved by a slight offset of the command.

For the semiconductors itself, the calculated values in the simulation results have to be compared with the datasheet. The IPLU300N04S4 can sustain an avalanche energy of 750mJ for a current of 150A [11]. Since up to 600A were flowing through one switch, with an avalanche energy of 442mJ, this value has been exceeded. Placing MOSFETs in parallel reduces the avalanche energy of a single device and the system might still work. However, the whole circuitry must be taken into account.

A deep knowledge of the system and all sub components of a fail-operational power distribution is required. Not going into a detailed analysis of the power distribution may lead to hazards which destroy safety relevant elements and safety strategies might fail. Semiconductors with proper circuits can detect problems and act very quick. Many problems can be avoided thereby, if the area of safe operation is being kept. Short circuits are usually low inductive and may be low ohmic. The rise of the current is only limited by the inductance of the supplying wires and supplies. Thin wires may quickly burn like a fuse, thicker cables will pull down the supplying voltage and safety systems might not work anymore - for automated vehicles this is hazardous. Influences on high ohmic short circuits need to be analyzed.

The avalanche effect on the SLS has not been analyzed. It can be easily calculated with the formulas given in [10] (equation 1). The path itself is a single wire with one load attached. Any short circuit event there will act far more quickly because the tripping point is set to the requirement of the load, while as the SBS and the B2B have to carry more power to supply - in theory the accumulated power of all loads. Thereby, increasing the tripping point for an short circuit event to a far higher limit. A failure between the SBS/B2B and the SLS can provide much more energy. A differential equation matrix for various initial values of currents and voltages could be set up. Finding the worst case could be done with an optimization method like Particle Swarm Optimization.

$$E_{AS} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot L \cdot I_{AS}^2 \cdot \frac{V_{AS}}{V_{AS} - V_{dd}} \quad (1)$$

In future work, we will verify the simulation results. For this purpose a hardware demonstrator is built.

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